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GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES TO DEVELOP RURAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Abstract

Entrepreneurs are playing very important role in the Indian economy. They identify the needs of the business, purchase the factors of production, coordinate them for some productive purposes, satisfy the needs of consumers, and result in increase the standard of Indian economy. They are the innovators, researchers and risk takers of the company.

Entrepreneurship development is important aspect in women empowerment. They face various problems in day to day work. A women needs encouraged to start a business in order to improve their economic standards as well as to improve their overall status in the economy. Women constitute half of the world's population accomplish two third of its working hours, receive one tenth of the world's income. They face many challenges and problems such as lack of family support, lack of capital, lack of self confidence, unaware of incentives and schemes laid down by the government. To overcome all these problems through the government various banks offer specialized loans exclusively for women that aim at promoting and easing out the process for them. A Present study is based on review of earlier studies and focuses on various government schemes to develop rural women entrepreneurship.

Key words: Women Entrepreneur, Steps taken by the government to develop women entrepreneurs in India, Various schemes offered by Banks

Introduction

Entrepreneurs are playing very important role in the Indian economy. Entrepreneurship development is important aspect in women empowerment. A women needs encouraged to start a business in order to improve their economic standards as well as to improve their overall status in the economy. Now a day's more women's are joining the world of business and entrepreneurship. All they need proper inspiration, training and promotions. Government of India launched a scheme "Trade related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development" (TREAD) during 9th plan period and also has taken few steps to develop the women entrepreneur by providing few trade related training programmes and awareness programme towards the extension activities related to trade, products, services.

Women Entrepreneurs

Women entrepreneur is defined as the women or a group of women, who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. The Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs as —an enterprise owned and controlled by women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated in the enterprise to women (Vinesh) 2014.

Review of literature

1. **Dr. Vijay Rathee and RituYadav (2017)** their study revealed on “**Role of Women Entrepreneurs in Economic Empowerment of Rural Areas**”. The study focuses on future prospects of women entrepreneurs and government initiatives for making women entrepreneurs more successful. Their study concluded that women entrepreneur increases because of their contribution in employment generation and revenue creation. The government has to play a facilitator, improve accessibility and schemes for empowering women efficient and effectively.
2. **Rakesh Kumar and Shruti Balhara (2017)** their study entitled on “**A Review on Issues and Supportive Measures for Growth of Women Entrepreneurship in India**” concluded that Women faces many issues while starting the enterprise but it is possible for a them to become a successful Entrepreneur when some help will be done by Government, Financial Institutions, and Family etc.
3. **Ruby Sinha (2017)** in her article “**Women Entrepreneurship in India**”. It is concluded that they need to believe in themselves and plunge in and they also have the ability to run a nation. They have to understand that the economy of their country is largely dependent on them and they need to work towards developing it at par with men.
4. **P. Manimalathi (2013)** her study entitled on “**Women entrepreneurs in Coimbatore district**”. This study concluded that women got a enough opportunities to start a business but they had to overcome come of the problems in order to sustain their business.
5. **Jalbert (2008)** conducted a study on “**Women Entrepreneurs in the Global Economy**”. It is examined how women’s business relation can build up women position in business and global trade. It is concluded that women posse specific traits like high energy level, personal skills and interpersonal skill that promote their creativity and generate new idea and way of execute.

Step taken by Government to Develop Women Entrepreneurs in India

The Government of India has also formulated various training and development cum employment generations programs for the women to start their ventures. These programmes are as follows:

Economic development and growth is not achieved fully without the development of women entrepreneurs. The Government of India has introduced the following schemes for promoting women entrepreneurship because the future of small scale industries depends upon the women-entrepreneurs:

1. **Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD):** Scheme was launched by Ministry of Small Industries to develop women entrepreneurs in rural, semi-urban and urban areas by developing entrepreneurial qualities
2. **Women Component Plan:** A special strategy adopted by Government to provide assistance to women entrepreneurs.
3. **Swarna Jayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana and Swarna Jayanti Shiksha Rozgar Yojana :** It was introduced by government to provide reservations for women and encouraging them to start their ventures.
4. **New schemes named Women Development Corporations :** Introduced by government to help women entrepreneurs in arranging credit and marketing facilities.
5. **State Industrial and Development Bank of India (SIDBI):** It has introduced following schemes to assist the women entrepreneurs. These schemes are:
 - a. Mahila Udyam Nidhi
 - b. Micro Credit Scheme for Women
 - c. Mahila Vikas Nidhi
 - d. Women Entrepreneurial Development Programmes
 - e. Marketing Development Fund for Women

Consortium of Women entrepreneurs of India

It provides a platform to assist the women entrepreneurs to develop new, creative and innovative techniques of production, finance and marketing. There are different bodies such as NGOs, voluntary organizations, Self-help groups, institutions and individual enterprises from rural and urban areas which collectively help the women entrepreneurs in their activities.

Training programmes

The following training schemes especially for the self employment of women are introduced by government:

- a. Support for Training and Employment Programme of Women (STEP).
- b. Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA).
- c. Small Industry Service Institutes (SISIs)
- d. State Financial Corporations
- e. National Small Industries Corporations
- f. District Industrial Centres (DICs)

Mahila Vikas Nidhi:

SIDBI has developed this fund for the entrepreneurial development of women especially in rural areas. Under Mahila Vikas Nidhi grants loan to women are given to start their venture in the field like spinning, weaving, knitting, embroidery products, block printing, handlooms handicrafts, bamboo products etc.

Rashtriya Mahila Kosh:

In 1993, Rashtriya Mahila Kosh was set up to grant micro credit to poor women at reasonable rates of interest with very low transaction costs and simple procedures.

Various schemes offered by Banks

1. Annapurna Scheme

This scheme is offered by the State Bank of Mysore for those women entrepreneurs who are setting up food catering industry in order to sell packed meals, snacks, etc. The amount granted as a loan under this scheme can be used to fulfil the working capital needs of the business like buying utensils and other kitchen tools and equipment.

Under this loan, a guarantor is required along with the assets of the business being pledged as collateral security. Further, the maximum amount of money that is granted is ₹50,000 which has to be repaid in monthly instalments for 36 months, however, after the loan is sanctioned, the lender doesn't have to pay the EMI for the first month. The interest rate is determined depending upon the market rate.

2. Stree Shakti Package For Women Entrepreneurs

This scheme is offered by most of the SBI branches to women who have 50% share in the ownership of a firm or business and have taken part in the state agencies run Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDP). The scheme also offers a discounted rate of interest by 0.50% in case the amount of loan is more than ₹2 lakhs.

3. Bharatiya Mahila Bank Business Loan

This loan is a support system for budding women entrepreneurs looking to start new ventures in the fields of the retail sector, loan against property, MICRO loans, and SME loans.

The maximum loan amount under this loan goes up to ₹20 crores in case of manufacturing industries and also a concession is available to the extent of 0.25% on the interest rate and interest rates usually range from 10.15% and higher.

Additionally, under the Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE), there is no requirement of collateral security for a loan of up to ₹1 crore.

4. Dena Shakti Scheme

This scheme is provided by Dena bank to those women entrepreneurs in the fields of agriculture, manufacturing, micro-credit, retail stores, or small enterprises; who are in need of financial assistance. The interest rate is also decreased by 0.25% along with the maximum loan amount being ₹20 lakhs for retail trade; education and housing whereas ₹50,000 under the microcredit

5. Udyogini Scheme

This scheme is offered by Punjab and Sind Bank so as to provide women entrepreneurs involved in Agriculture, retail and small business enterprises to get loans for business at flexible terms and concessional interest rates. The maximum amount of loan under this scheme for women between the age of 18-45 years is ₹1 lakhs but family income is also taken into consideration and is set at ₹45,000 per annum for SC/ST women.

6. Cent Kalyani Scheme

This scheme is offered by the Central Bank of India with the aim of supporting women in starting a new venture or expanding or modifying an existing enterprise. This loan can be availed by women who are involved in village and cottage industries, micro, small and medium enterprises, self-employed women, agriculture and allied activities, retail trade, and government-sponsored programs.

This scheme requires no collateral security or guarantor and charges no processing fees. And the maximum amount that can be granted under the scheme is Rs. 100 lakhs.

7. Mahila Udyam Nidhi Scheme

This scheme is launched by Punjab National Bank and aims at supporting the women entrepreneurs involved in the small scale industries by granting them soft loans that can be repaid over a period of 10 years. Under this scheme there are different plans for beauty parlors, day care centres, purchase of auto rickshaws, two-wheelers, cars, etc. the maximum amount granted under this scheme is ₹10 lakhs and the interest depends upon the market rates.

8. Mudra Yojana Scheme for Women

This scheme has been launched by the Govt. of India for individual women wanting to start small new enterprises and businesses like beauty parlors, tailoring units, tuition centres, etc. as well as a group of women wanting to start a venture together. The loan doesn't require any collateral security and can be availed as per 3 schemes –

- i. Shishu – loan amount is limited to ₹50,000 and can be availed by those businesses that are in their initial stages.
- ii. Kishor – loan amount ranges between ₹50,000 and ₹5 lakhs and can be availed by those who have a well-established enterprise.
- iii. Tarun – loan amount is ₹10 lakhs and can be availed by those businesses that are well established but require further funds for the purpose of expansion

If the loan is granted, a Mudra card will be given to functions the same way as a credit card however the funds available are limited to 10% of the loan amount granted to them.

9. Orient Mahila Vikas Yojana Scheme

This scheme is provided by Oriental Bank of Commerce to those women who hold a 51% share capital individually or jointly in a proprietary concern. No collateral security is required for loans of ₹10 lakhs up to ₹25 lakhs in case of small-scale industries and the period of repayment is 7 years. A concession on the interest rate of up to 2% is given.

Conclusion

Women entrepreneur are one of the main pillars for the economic development. There are numerous schemes provided to assist women entrepreneurs by the government, scheduled and non scheduled banks in our country. But the government should focus to act as facilitator and create a awareness programme on various schemes imposed by them for empowerment of rural women effectively and efficiently to implement them. Development of rural women entrepreneurs does not mean development of women in rural areas but it mean development of entire society with economic growth.

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